

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	30 months

Deliverable information

WP	9
Deliverable related number	D31
Deliverable number	D9.1
Deliverable name	National Precision Initiatives
Deliverable Description	Results of national precision oncology initiatives. Electronic, English, 29 pages Online database
Lead Beneficiary	Jessa Hospital
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	03
Due Date	31/01/2025
Delivery Date	11/03/2025
Approval Date	

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
01	23/12/2024	Initial version	Jessa Hospital, BE
02	30/01/2025	Revised after input from contributors	Jessa Hospital, BE
03	11/03/2025	Reference to publication of BALLETT study data added	Jessa Hospital, BE

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1. Background and Objectives of CAN.HEAL Work Package 9: Treatment and Follow-Up

Background

The CAN.HEAL project, funded by the European Commission, aims to bridge the gap between genomics and public health to improve cancer outcomes across the European Union. Work Package 9 (WP9) focuses on the treatment and follow-up of cancer patients, emphasizing the integration of personalised medicine approaches into routine clinical care. This involves establishing national and international systems for comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP), clinical decision-making through molecular tumour boards (MTBs), and improved access to innovative treatments.

WP9 centres on three key pillars:

- **Broad access to CGP:** Promoting the decentralized implementation of comprehensive genomic testing to identify actionable genetic alterations and biomarkers that guide personalised treatment decisions for advanced cancer patients.
- **Harmonization of biomarker-driven treatment recommendations:** examining the value MTBs to facilitate consistent and informed treatment recommendations based on genomic biomarker data.
- **Sustainable integration of precision oncology:** Precision oncology requires overcoming financial and logistical barriers to make advanced genomic testing accessible across diverse healthcare settings. This pillar focuses on generating evidence for clinical and economic benefits, supporting healthcare reimbursement, and fostering cross-sector partnerships to ensure that personalised cancer treatments are equitably available and sustainably integrated into standard care.

Objectives of WP9:

- **Evaluate the clinical value of CGP in real-world practice:** By collecting and analysing data from CGP, WP9 aims to understand how these insights translate into broader access to precision oncology and better therapeutic options for cancer patients.
- **Implement standardized CGP across Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) laboratories:** Focus on consistent CGP wet-lab performance, data analysis, clinical interpretation, and treatment recommendations using standardized protocols.
- **Quantify access to innovative drugs:** Assess patient access to drugs guided by CGP and MTBs, whether through standard-of-care, clinical trials, medical need programs, or off-label use.

- **Attract more innovative treatments and clinical trials to the European Union (EU):**
Use a multi-stakeholder approach to draw innovative therapies and trials to the region, thereby increasing accessibility and clinical options for patients.

This report outlines the activities and results related to these objectives, addressing key ongoing challenges and providing EU-focused policy recommendations based on the findings of this WP.

2. Key activities and collaborative efforts

To achieve the objectives of WP9, a series of coordinated activities were undertaken, focusing on building a framework for precision oncology and developing actionable insights for EU-wide policy. These activities were essential in addressing the challenges of implementing precision oncology across diverse healthcare systems and were designed to ensure rigorous collaboration, data sharing, and process standardisation. The primary activities included the following:

Regular meetings and stakeholder discussions

While the organization and coordination of meetings were led by WP1 (Management and coordination), WP9 actively participated in these recurring sessions to align objectives, review progress, and refine strategies. These meetings brought together diverse stakeholders from within the CAN.HEAL partnership, including researchers, medical specialists, policy experts, and healthcare representatives. These meetings provided an environment of knowledge exchange, addressing challenges and collaboratively exploring solutions and further steps aligned with the broader goals of CAN.HEAL.

Inter-WP collaboration

Recognizing the importance of a cohesive approach, WP9 collaborated closely with other WPs, particularly WP8 (Molecular Tumour Boards) (Institut Curie, France) and WP10 (oncology Decision Support Tools, DST) (Sciensano, Belgium), which had complementary objectives. This cross-package collaboration was instrumental in harmonizing efforts, optimizing resource use, and ensuring that precision oncology recommendations were grounded in a comprehensive understanding of the project's scope. While a key aspect of this partnership involved capacity building and the execution of a survey mapping NGS and MTB activities, as well as DST use across the EU (Figure 1; further elaborated in D9.2¹), the collaboration also encompassed broader strategic alignment, knowledge exchange, and the development of a unified approach to supporting precision oncology within CAN.HEAL.

¹ CAN.HEAL D9.2 Capacity building: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

Figure 1: collaboration framework within CAN.HEAL for the mapping of NGS and MTB activities and the use of DSTs through a EU-wide survey.²

WP9 also collaborated with WP3 (Evaluation, Equity and Impact Assessment) (AQuAS, Spain; FISABIO, Spain; NKI, The Netherlands), by evaluating readiness and equity specifically for its use case, the BALLETT study, which focused on introducing CGP + MTB for precision oncology. This collaboration helped WP3 create recommendations that address the practical implementation needs and equitable access considerations of CGP + MTB.³ Finally, WP9 more specifically contributed to a Health Technology Assessment (HTA) study by NKI, The Netherlands (WP3) by providing the full BALLETT study data. This data enabled WP3 to generate evidence to support decisions on implementing and reimbursing CGP + MTB. This partnership provided insights into cost-effectiveness, impact and other value, though certain limitations remained.⁴

The recommendations presented in this report are, in part, based on the insights and outcomes derived from this extensive inter-WP collaboration and exchange.

The BALLETT study as a Use Case

A cornerstone of WP9's activities was the BALLETT study, which served as a practical application and use case for implementing CGP combined with an MTB (CGP + MTB) in a real-world, multicentre setting. Through BALLETT, WP9 aimed to assess the feasibility, impact, and scalability of CGP-driven treatment recommendations for patients with advanced cancers. Weekly laboratory meetings were held to standardize CGP processes

² CAN.HEAL D9.2: Capacity building at Zenodo: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

³ CAN.HEAL D3.1: Evaluation plan and assessment tool, D3.2: Equity guide and D3.4: Evaluation guide-report at Zenodo: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

⁴ CAN.HEAL D3.3 DMIA tool at Zenodo: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

across the nine participating NGS laboratories, ensuring consistency in data quality and diagnostic accuracy. Simultaneously, weekly national MTB meetings allowed multidisciplinary experts to review CGP results, discuss patient cases, and provide treatment recommendations, facilitating multi-centre collaboration and patient referrals. These meetings also facilitated ongoing education and alignment among stakeholders, reinforcing the project's commitment to high-quality, patient-centred care.

Data collection, analysis, and reporting

In collaboration with data analysts and bioinformaticians, WP9 established a standardized process for collecting, analysing, and reporting genomic data from the BALLETT study. This rigorous approach allowed WP9 to derive actionable insights from the study, identify persistent challenges, and inform policy recommendations. Additionally, WP9 focused on capturing real-world evidence regarding the benefits and limitations of CGP + MTB, which is crucial for guiding policy development at the EU level. A full report on the BALLETT study is published and available via open access in NPJ Precision Oncology.⁵

Development of policy recommendations

Drawing on the insights and evidence generated from these activities, WP9 formulated targeted recommendations to inform EU policies on precision oncology. These recommendations emphasize accessibility, standardisation, and sustainability, aiming to guide the integration of comprehensive genomic tumour testing into routine clinical practice across EU healthcare systems.

Overall, these activities have enabled WP9 to make substantial progress in understanding the operational, equity, and readiness requirements for precision oncology, while providing evidence for national and EU policy. Through the BALLETT study and strategic collaborations, WP9 has generated essential insights into the potential and limitations of CGP + MTB, highlighting key steps and considerations needed to implement precision oncology effectively and equitably across diverse healthcare systems.

3. Comprehensive Genomic Profiling: types, benefits and challenges

One of the crucial pillars WP9 centres on is the importance and implementation of high-throughput molecular assays like CGP in precision oncology. Here we first describe the technical, clinical, and regulatory dimensions of molecular diagnostics in cancer care, emphasizing the benefits and challenges of these advanced technologies.

Key benefits of CGP and other high-throughput assays

CGP and high-throughput molecular assays have revolutionized cancer diagnostics, forming the backbone of personalised oncology (Figure 2). These assays allow for a broad analysis

⁵ Volders, P.J., Aftimos, P., Dedeurwaerdere, F. *et al.* [A nationwide comprehensive genomic profiling and molecular tumor board platform for patients with advanced cancer](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0) *npj Precis. Onc.* **9**, 66 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0>

of genetic alterations, including single nucleotide variants (SNVs), copy-number variations (CNVs), aberrant fusion genes or structural variants (SVs), and complex biomarkers like microsatellite instability (MSI), tumour mutational burden (TMB), and homologous recombination deficiency (HRD). By enabling a comprehensive view of the cancer genome, these assays can identify actionable mutations and biomarkers for selecting targeted treatments and immunotherapies, guiding treatment decisions, enrolling patients in clinical trials, and facilitating referral to genetic counselling when germline alterations are suspected.

Figure 2: Comprehensive genomic profiling

Types of assays and their applications

Gene Panel Sequencing

Now a standard in clinical diagnostics, gene panels target specific genes associated with cancer, enabling rapid and efficient profiling. CGP refers to gene panel sequencing typically covering several hundreds of genes, allowing the analysis of the full spectrum of genomic biomarkers, including complex markers like TMB, MSI and HRD.

Whole-Exome and Whole-Genome Sequencing (WES and WGS)

Offering broad genomic coverage, WES and WGS go beyond targeted panels by examining all coding regions or the entire genome. Although WGS is the most thorough, it faces challenges with cost, computational demands, and implementation.

Whole-Transcriptome Sequencing (WTS)

Focused on RNA, WTS identifies fusion genes and gene expression signatures linked to clinical outcomes. Although less established for routine diagnostics, it holds promise, particularly in conjunction with WGS or WES.

Array-Based Technologies

Genomic and methylation arrays are applied in certain cancer subtypes, such as central nervous system tumours, to identify subtype-specific profiles and improve classification.

Advantages for patient outcomes

Studies show that patients with advanced cancers who undergo genome-based treatment matching have significantly better outcomes than those treated based on empirical treatment of physician's choice. Additionally, high-throughput genomic testing improves operational efficiencies by optimizing the use of tissue samples, consolidating diagnostic methods, and reducing labour and costs in the laboratory setting.

Implementation challenges

Despite the advantages, widespread implementation of CGP and other high-throughput assays faces several barriers:

High costs and reimbursement issues

The high costs of high-throughput genomic assays compared to traditional single-gene tests present significant challenges, especially in regions with constrained public healthcare budgets. Healthcare systems often require robust evidence of cost-effectiveness and clinical benefit before they commit to reimbursing these advanced diagnostics. However, generating such evidence is inherently difficult due to the need for long-term studies that demonstrate improved patient outcomes and cost savings from targeted therapies. This creates a paradox where funding is needed to produce the evidence that would justify broader reimbursement, yet without initial reimbursement, comprehensive data collection is financially and logistically challenging. Notably, the costs of biomarker testing are relatively low compared to the expenses associated with administering costly therapies without molecular stratification, such as immunotherapies, highlighting the potential for cost savings through more precise patient selection. Consequently, delays in evidence generation can hinder timely access to innovative diagnostics and treatments for patients.

Quality, technical, infrastructural, and standardisation barriers.

High-throughput genomic assays require advanced sequencing technologies, sophisticated bioinformatics tools, and trained personnel to interpret complex genomic data, which are often only available at specialized centres. The lack of standardisation across laboratories, including differing protocols and result interpretations, further complicates its broader adoption. Without unified standards and substantial infrastructural investment, widespread integration of high-throughput genomic assays remains challenging.

Education and awareness of healthcare professionals

The rapid pace of advancements in genomics and the nuances of biomarker-based therapies require ongoing education, yet structured training programs in this area are limited. Without adequate knowledge and confidence in using broad genomic data, healthcare providers may underutilize this powerful tool, ultimately limiting patients' access to personalised cancer treatments that could improve outcomes.

Regulatory and ethical constraints

With the introduction of the EU's In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation (IVDR), new standards for molecular assay validation and patient data security are essential. The regulation mandates compliance for diagnostic labs, particularly those using in-house (IH) in vitro diagnostics, which need to meet stringent quality and performance standards. Furthermore, data privacy and the ethical implications of incidental findings demand careful handling to maintain patient trust.

Supporting infrastructure

Molecular Tumour Boards (MTB) and Decision Support Tools (DST): The complexity of molecular data interpretation requires robust support from MTBs and DSTs. MTBs facilitate multidisciplinary decision-making by integrating inputs from oncologists, pathologists, molecular biologists, and bioinformaticians. DST platforms help automate variant classification and match patients with appropriate drugs and/or clinical trials. These tools are crucial for ensuring consistency in biomarker interpretation and enhancing precision in clinical trial matching, although challenges in data standardisation persist.

4. WP9 use case: The BALLETT study

Introduction and objectives

The outcomes of this WP, centred on CGP + MTB as a foundational element, are largely based on practical insights gained from the BALLETT study as the primary use case. The set-up of the BALLETT study, its results, limitations and challenges are reported in the published manuscript available via open access in NPJ Precision Oncology.⁶

The BALLETT study, part of the Belgian Society of Medical Oncology's (BSMO) PRECISION initiative, was designed to explore the feasibility and clinical impact of implementing a standardized CGP + MTB approach for advanced cancer patients across Belgium.

The primary objectives of the BALLETT study were to assess CGP's utility in a real-world setting, streamline the workflow for genomic testing across multiple labs in a decentralized way, and provide consistent treatment recommendations through a national MTB (nMTB). To achieve this, the study enrolled patients with advanced solid tumours from 12 hospitals, incorporating both academic and non-academic sites. CGP was performed using the off-

⁶ Volders, P.J., Aftimos, P., Dedeurwaerdere, F. *et al.* [A nationwide comprehensive genomic profiling and molecular tumor board platform for patients with advanced cancer](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0) *npj Precis. Onc.* **9**, 66 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0>

the-shelf, standardized TruSight Oncology 500 (TSO500, Illumina) assay in a consortium of nine Belgian laboratories, ensuring uniform methodology and quality control across all sites. Patient data were reviewed in weekly meetings by the centralized nMTB that included multidisciplinary experts who provided treatment recommendations based on CGP results. A workflow diagram of the study cases is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3: BALLETT study workflow. Workflow diagram, illustrating the process from patient recruitment to treatment recommendation.

This decentralized setup, initiated by the BSMO and supported by industry and public health collaborations, aimed to make precision oncology more accessible, evaluate logistical feasibility, and identify barriers to implementing a CGP + nMTB model in Belgium's healthcare system.

Overcoming existing barriers

The BALLETT study was strategically designed to address all the critical barriers discussed above to implementing CGP in routine clinical oncology by taking a decentralized, standardized, and multi-stakeholder approach. Here's how the study tackled these challenges:

Cost and funding: The BALLETT study aimed to bridge the financial gap by partnering with the scientific organization of medical oncologists BSMO, industrial stakeholders (Illumina, Velsera, OncoDNA) and Belgium's national health institution, Sciensano. This collaboration allowed for broad CGP access without upfront cost constraints on patients, offering a model for addressing the high costs associated with CGP. By securing external funding, the study aimed to generate the necessary evidence to potentially support future reimbursement decisions.

Standardisation and infrastructure: BALLETT implemented a uniform methodology across nine local laboratories to ensure consistent quality and reliability of CGP results. By using the off-the-shelf, standardized TSO500 assay across all sites, the study ensured that data generated from different labs were directly comparable. This approach addressed quality and infrastructural challenges, demonstrating that CGP can be decentralized without sacrificing accuracy or consistency.

Technical and logistical barriers: The study utilized a coordinated weekly sample scheduling system and a custom-designed web app (BALLETT-app) to manage and visualize patient data. This infrastructure optimized the workflow, improved turnaround times, and facilitated seamless data sharing between labs and the nMTB. Weekly nMTB meetings using the BALLETT-app for data visualization and presentation allowed harmonized discussions on treatment recommendations, overcoming technical hurdles related to data interpretation and ensuring timely clinical decision-making.

Clinical decision support and education: The nMTB, which included oncologists, pathologists, geneticists, and bioinformaticians, provided consolidated treatment recommendations based on CGP results. This collaborative structure not only facilitated standardized decision-making but also served as a valuable educational platform for healthcare providers, addressing the knowledge gap surrounding CGP and enhancing professionals' confidence in interpreting and acting on genomic data.

Broad access and equity: By enrolling patients from 12 hospitals, both academic and non-academic and geographically spread across Belgium, the study aimed to make CGP accessible to a diverse patient population. This design increased the potential for equitable access to precision oncology, countering typical disparities seen in high-tech cancer care.

Treatment access: The primary objective of the BALLETT study was to expand treatment options for cancer patients by enhancing their access to innovative therapies. Through the nMTB, patients received treatment recommendations based on CGP, which identified a broad array of potentially actionable biomarkers. These recommendations included approved therapies, clinical trial opportunities, compassionate use programs, and off-label treatment options. By utilizing a CGP assay that captures a wide range of actionable markers, the study was able to match patients to a more diverse set of drug options and clinical trials.

Summary of results

For a more extensive report on the results of the BALLETT study, we refer to the full publication in NPJ Precision Oncology.⁷

The BALLETT study assessed the feasibility and impact of implementing a nationwide CGP + MTB platform in Belgium to guide precision oncology for patients with advanced cancers.

⁷ Volders, P.J., Aftimos, P., Dedeurwaerdere, F. *et al.* [A nationwide comprehensive genomic profiling and molecular tumor board platform for patients with advanced cancer](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0) *npj Precis. Onc.* **9**, 66 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-025-00858-0>

Patient enrolment and CGP success rate: The study enrolled 872 patients across 12 hospitals, both academic and non-academic, with a broad variety of advanced solid tumour types (n=32) (Figure 4). Eligible patients were adults (>18 years) with metastatic or locally advanced solid tumours, of any type, preferably in early treatment lines to enhance clinical trial enrolment. They required a life expectancy >12 weeks, ECOG ≤2, no severe organ dysfunction, and a recent (<2 years) biopsy with >10% tumour cells for CGP analysis. CGP was successfully performed for 756 patients (93% success rate).

Figure 4: BALLETT study flow: General overview of the BALLETT study recruitment, success rate, and treatment recommendation rates.

Turnaround Time: The median time from patient inclusion to nMTB report was 29 days, highlighting the potential for integrating CGP results into clinical decision-making within a practical timeframe. However, turnaround times varied significantly across sites (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Turnaround-time (TAT) at the participating sites. TAT is measured as the days between signing the informed consent form and delivering the report to the treating clinician. The median TAT was 29 days, yet differences between the sites are apparent.

Actionable findings and genomic alterations: CGP identified actionable genomic alterations in 81% of patients, significantly higher than the estimated 23% if only standard-of-care diagnostic gene panels had been used.⁸ This underscored CGP's ability to reveal more treatment opportunities through biomarkers like emerging predictive gene alterations and complex markers such as TMB, MSI, and HRD.

The actionability in the different tumour types is illustrated in figure 6, also demonstrating the distribution across clinical classes as assessed by the AMP/ASCO/CAP tiering system with Tier IA or IB, strong clinical significance, Tier IIC and IID, potential clinical significance and Tier III, unknown clinical significance.⁹

Figure 6: Distribution of actionable markers across tiers with strong clinical significance (IA, IB), potential clinical significance (IIC and IID), and uncertain clinical significance (IIIA) by tumour type.

⁸ In Belgium, the ComPerMed NGS panels are the standard-of-care for diagnostics and reimbursement (www.ComPerMed.be). These guidelines focus on EMA-approved gene alterations, limiting their use to tumour types with EMA-approved drugs and excluding detection of alterations with potential clinical significance.

⁹ Li, M. M. *et al.* Standards and Guidelines for the Interpretation and Reporting of Sequence Variants in Cancer: A Joint Consensus Recommendation of the Association for Molecular Pathology, American Society of Clinical Oncology, and College of American Pathologists. *J. Mol. Diagn.* **19**, 4-23, doi:10.1016/j.jmoldx.2016.10.002 (2017).

MTB recommendations: The nMTB provided CGP-based treatment recommendations for 69% of patients with successful CGP. Recommendations included approved treatments, access to clinical trials, compassionate use programs, and off-label drug options. For 15% of patients, actionable alterations were found, but treatment recommendations could not be made due to drug inaccessibility in Belgium or lack of nearby clinical trials.

Treatment uptake: Despite receiving nMTB recommendations, only 23% of patients were able to follow through with the suggested matched treatments. Reasons for non-implementation included physician discretion, limited clinical trial availability in proximity to patients, and rapid disease progression.

Incidental findings: CGP detected potential germline variants in 15% of cases, prompting recommendations for genetic counselling. This finding highlighted an additional benefit of CGP in identifying hereditary cancer risks for patients and their families.

In summary, the BALLETT study demonstrated the feasibility and benefits of a standardized CGP + MTB model, achieving a high actionability rate and providing valuable insights for patient care.

Limitations and challenges

Despite its successes, the BALLETT study also identified several limitations and challenges in implementing a CGP + MTB approach, highlighting obstacles that still need to be addressed for broader adoption in clinical oncology:

Limited innovative treatment access

Although actionable genetic markers were found in 81% of patients, 15% did not receive a treatment recommendation. This gap may be due to several factors:

Firstly, drug accessibility after European Medicines Agency (EMA) approval might be delayed. A recent study on drug access in six European countries found that the time to access may differ in different countries of the EU and that hospitals in Belgium had slower access than Italy and France.¹⁰

Secondly, clinical trials involving matched drugs may be conducted exclusively abroad, possibly not even within Europe. This underscores the importance of expert review by nMTB members actively involved in conducting clinical trials. An up-to-date clinical trial database for trials active in Belgium, as was recently established by BSMO,¹¹ will increase the usefulness of MTB recommendations. Of note, the BSMO PRECISION initiative might have itself played a role in attracting more clinical trials to Belgium.

Thirdly, Belgium currently lacks a large, nationwide trial akin to the DRUP trial in the Netherlands, which has been instrumental in facilitating access to targeted therapies and

¹⁰ Vancoppenolle, J. M., Franzen, N., Koole, S. N., Retel, V. P. & van Harten, W. H. Differences in time to patient access to innovative cancer medicines in six European countries. *Int. J. Cancer* 154, 886-894, doi:10.1002/ijc.34753 (2023)

¹¹ Cancertrials.be: [Cancer Trials - Recruiting for oncology trials in Belgium](#)

evaluating their efficacy. In anticipation of establishing a comparable pan-cancer, multi-drug basket trial in Belgium, it would be crucial to integrate this effort within broader European initiatives. Such a trial should align with ongoing EU-funded cross-border precision oncology projects like PCM4EU¹² and PRIME-ROSE¹³, which offer valuable models and insights for structuring, regulating, and scaling precision oncology initiatives. Embedding a Belgian DRUP-like trial within these larger European contexts would enhance collaboration, streamline regulatory pathways, and facilitate wider access to CGP, ultimately supporting Belgium’s alignment with European strategies to expand access to innovative cancer therapies.

Leveraging the practical experience gained from the BALLETT study, alongside insights from CAN.HEAL and other large European projects, would be essential to ensure the successful establishment and sustainability of a DRUP-like trial in Belgium and other EU countries.

Low uptake of treatment recommendations

Of the 69% of patients who received a CGP-based treatment recommendation, only 23% ultimately received the matched treatment. A key reason for this low uptake was physicians’ discretion to pursue alternative treatment options, often due to the type of genomic variants identified (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Treatment recommendations uptake. Uptake rate of the nMTB recommendations and reasons for deviation from recommendations across participating hospitals in the BALLETT study. MNP: Medical need program.

Many of the detected actionable variants were categorized as tier IID, meaning although actionable they had limited clinical evidence regarding their effectiveness. These variants often led to recommendations for early-phase (Phase I/II) clinical trials, which may not

¹² <https://www.matrix-fkb.no/en/pcm4eu/home>

¹³ <https://www.matrix-fkb.no/en/prime-rose/home>

provide as strong a basis for decision-making compared to later-phase trials or approved treatments. Physicians may be cautious about relying on early-phase trials, as these are primarily designed to test safety, dosage, and preliminary efficacy, rather than offering confirmed therapeutic benefit. Additionally, the trials matched to these variants can require significant commitments from patients, including more intensive monitoring and visits, as well as the possibility of unknown side effects. Given these factors, physicians may prefer established treatment protocols as far as still available (e.g. another chemotherapy line). This highlights an inherent challenge in implementing CGP: while CGP can reveal numerous potential targets, the clinical actionability and attractiveness of these options are often constrained by the maturity of evidence available for certain variants and the trial phase associated with them.

Additionally, also patients often declined the recommended treatment when the clinical trial was located too far from their residence (Figure 7), highlighting access barriers to novel therapies and underscoring the need for a broader roll-out of clinical studies both across Belgium and Europe. These findings also emphasize the value of decentralized clinical trials, though this would require a significant shift in how cancer trials are planned, implemented, and conducted.

Decentralized clinical trials (DCTs) are trials conducted with reduced reliance on centralized trial sites, allowing patients to participate without the need for frequent travel to specific clinical locations. Instead, DCTs leverage technology, local healthcare providers, and other resources to bring the trial directly to patients' communities. This approach offers several **advantages**, including improved access for patients who live far from major research centres, enhanced participant diversity, and potentially faster recruitment. **Requirements** include robust digital infrastructure (telemedicine, mobile apps), partnerships with local providers, remote monitoring technology, flexible regulatory frameworks, and secure data management. **Challenges** involve ensuring data privacy, standardizing practices across sites, managing regulatory differences, addressing patients' digital literacy, coordinating with local providers, and retaining patient engagement. DCTs hold promise but require significant support in technology, regulation, and patient management to be effective.

Another common reason for deviation was patients' deteriorating health, indicating that CGP-informed treatment selection should occur earlier in the disease course. Implementing CGP at the time of diagnosis for all patients with advanced cancer could allow for more strategic treatment planning and facilitate earlier genome-directed therapies, rather than reserving these options as last-resort measures. Additionally, while window-of-opportunity trials primarily aim at biomarker discovery rather than therapeutic benefit, their integration

at an earlier stage could still contribute to refining patient selection for targeted treatments in later disease stages.

Window-of opportunity clinical trials are short-term studies in cancer research that allow patients to try a new treatment during a natural pause in their standard care, such as right after diagnosis or between treatment lines. These trials allow researchers to study the new drug's effects without delaying standard care.

For patients, the trials offer early access to innovative therapies and more personalised care, with frequent monitoring to track how the tumour responds. Researchers use these trials to identify biomarkers, gain insight into how the drug works, and determine if it's worth pursuing in larger trials. While results aren't guaranteed, these trials can help guide future treatment decisions and may offer promising options for patients seeking additional therapy.

While the applicability of window-of-opportunity trials in advanced cancer patients may be more limited compared to early-stage patients, they might be valuable when designed carefully, especially in patients with limited treatment options.

Variability in treatment recommendation uptake across hospitals

There were significant differences in how participating hospitals implemented nMTB recommendations, with some sites showing minimal adherence. This variability may stem from differences in infrastructure, clinical trial availability, or physician education levels, underscoring the need for consistent training and support in precision oncology.

Technical and logistical challenges

Despite a standardized workflow, some local variability in CGP success rates and turnaround times was observed. Factors like sample quality, DNA/RNA extraction methods, and inter-operator differences affected result consistency, suggesting a need for further standardisation and quality control across labs.

Complex data interpretation and decision support

A significant challenge in this study was standardizing treatment recommendations within the nMTB. A custom-designed app (BALLET-app) for data visualization proved indispensable, enabling structured, harmonized discussions among nMTB members. However, matching drugs and clinical trials to specific genetic targets largely required manual searches in online databases and the use of two separate tertiary NGS data analysis systems available for the study. While these systems offered some automated matching, manual filtering and careful selection of trials were still necessary to ensure that recommendations were relevant and suitable for each patient's cancer history.

Developing a comprehensive, user-friendly, and regularly updated decision support tool (DST) is essential to assist healthcare professionals in interpreting complex genomic data and generating consistent, evidence-based treatment recommendations. This need is further explored in WP10, where the development of a standardized DST is prioritized.¹⁴ WP9 has advised WP10 on this topic, drawing on insights and practical experience from the BALLETT study to inform tool design and functionality. Such a tool would streamline decision-making, enhance the efficiency of MTB operations, and further contribute to the standardisation of CGP-based interventions across various settings. For more information on the EU-oncDST concept: see CAN.HEAL D10.1.⁷

Evidence Generation for Reimbursement

Leveraging the findings from BALLETT to inform reimbursement decisions within the healthcare systems remains challenging. Future analyses will examine whether the patients have benefited in terms of progression-free survival (PFS) ratios upon completion of follow-up. However, the potential for observing significantly improved clinical outcomes is limited by the relatively small proportion of patients who received the matched treatment and by the real-world study design without a control cohort. To effectively engage stakeholders, it will be crucial to present data on compelling economic outcomes as well. For that purpose, the BALLETT study database is further utilized for healthcare technology assessments by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI, Amsterdam) as part of the CAN.HEAL WP 3.¹⁵

Overall, the study demonstrated the feasibility of CGP + MTB in a decentralized setting but underscored the importance of overcoming persistent challenges related to drug access, treatment implementation, hospital infrastructure, and data support systems to realize CGP's full potential in clinical practice.

5. Findings from a micro-costing benchmark study on NGS

As part of WP9 Task 9.1, a benchmark study was conducted to assess the total expenses associated with NGS as performed by Belgian laboratories. The study involved six laboratories and revealed significant financial challenges related to the current reimbursement model. The study setup and results are outlined in Annex 1.

Reimbursement level at the time of the study (Q2 2023): The Belgian NGS convention established a reimbursement rate of approximately €360 per test for DNA-based NGS, indexed slightly from the original rate of €350. This rate was set based on smaller DNA panels testing hot-spot regions. However, as the range of required tests has expanded to include comprehensive exome coverage and additional tumour suppressor genes, the current rate no longer covers actual costs.

¹⁴ CAN.HEAL D10.1 EU-oncDST at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497907>

¹⁵ CAN.HEAL D3.3 DMIA tool at Zenodo: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

Costs for DNA panels and CGP: The actual costs of performing DNA-only NGS panels ranged from €544 to €1,005 per test, with all participating laboratories incurring losses of €184 to €645 per test due to the insufficient reimbursement rate. Panels that included RNA sequencing or comprehensive profiling costs ranged higher, from €680 to €2,049. Costs for comprehensive panels capable of detecting MSI and TMB were estimated at approximately €1,832 to €1,887 per test, far exceeding the current reimbursement rate.

Implications of cost discrepancy: The study highlighted that reimbursement tariffs are not cost-effective for any of the tested panels, leading to significant financial burdens for the laboratories and hospitals involved.

We are referring to D9.2 (Capacity building) which elaborates further on NGS reimbursement rates across the EU countries, based on a survey that was conducted to map and evaluate the NGS practices in the EU.

The findings of this study were used to inform the Belgian Health Care authorities based on which reimbursement tariffs were adapted starting from July 1st, 2024 onwards. The new tariffs were part of a global reorganization of NGS reimbursement through the new “NGS convention”.

6. Future Perspectives

Looking forward, advancing precision oncology will depend on innovative technologies that enhance drug response predictions and enable real-time monitoring of patients' treatment progress. **Multi-omics approaches** - integrating genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics - offer a more comprehensive view of tumour biology, potentially allowing for more accurate predictions of treatment efficacy. Additionally, **drug screening using patient-derived tumour cell cultures and organoids** provides a promising method to test therapeutic effectiveness in environments closely resembling patients' actual tumours, thereby supporting more individualized treatment strategies.

Liquid biopsy testing is also transforming cancer care by enabling minimally invasive monitoring of cancer-related genetic changes. See WP7 (Early detection) and WP11 (NGS including liquid biopsy). These tests can be used for **real-time tracking of treatment response**, detecting **minimal residual disease (MRD)**, and identifying early signs of relapse, offering valuable insights into tumour evolution and emerging resistance mutations to help guide treatment adjustments.

For EU-funded projects focused on implementation, it is crucial to include **translational WPs** that support the development of these emerging technologies. Biobanking efforts should be an integral component, ensuring the collection of high-quality, patient-derived samples necessary for validating these advanced technologies. This integration will facilitate the smooth transition from research to clinical application, ultimately driving more personalised and adaptive cancer care across Europe.

7. Recommendations for the EU

Promote decentralized genomic testing for equitable access across the EU

Rationale: Access to advanced testing methodologies is often limited by regional disparities, where patients far from specialized centres may face barriers to testing. Decentralized, affordable genomic testing, would make these services more accessible, reducing inequities across regions and improving timely access to precision diagnostics for all patients.

Recommendation: The EU should support and promote decentralized genomic testing networks and infrastructure to enhance equitable access. By expanding testing capabilities to local or regional levels, patients across all EU member states can benefit from advanced genomic diagnostics regardless of their geographic location.

Next Steps: Allocate EU funding to establish decentralized genomic testing facilities in underserved regions and develop frameworks that enable cross-border collaboration. This includes building digital infrastructure and standardizing protocols for remote genomic testing and analysis to maintain quality and consistency across decentralized sites.

Harmonize and expand Molecular Tumour Boards across the EU

Rationale:

MTBs are essential for integrating genomic data into clinical decision-making for personalised cancer treatment. While the CAN.HEAL project has developed MTB guidelines¹⁶, other frameworks also exist, leading to fragmentation and inconsistent implementation across the EU. Harmonization of these guidelines can ensure standardized and equitable access to high-quality MTB services.

Recommendation:

The EU should support harmonizing existing MTB guidelines, including those from CAN.HEAL and other initiatives, to establish consistent standards. This effort should also focus on expanding access to MTBs across all regions, ensuring equitable integration into oncology care.

Next Steps:

- Facilitate an EU-wide review to align and integrate guidelines from CAN.HEAL and other initiatives into a unified framework.
- Provide funding to establish and expand MTBs in underserved regions.

¹⁶ CAN.HEAL WP8 (MTB) deliverables: [Search CAN.HEAL - Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics Platform](#)

- Develop digital infrastructure for virtual MTBs to promote cross-border collaboration and expertise sharing.
- Monitor and evaluate the implementation of harmonized guidelines to improve quality and outcomes continuously.

Enhance access to innovative therapies and expand large-scale clinical trials

Rationale: Limited access to novel drugs, coupled with regional disparities in trial availability, hinders the effective deployment of precision oncology across Europe.

Recommendation: The EU should support a multi-drug clinical trial framework similar to the Dutch DRUP initiative to streamline access and assess the efficacy of targeted therapies across member states. Belgium, among other EU countries, lacks a large, nationwide trial comparable to DRUP, which could facilitate access to innovative therapies and evaluate their efficacy. Establishing a pan-cancer, multi-drug basket across the EU, aligned with existing large-scale projects like PCM4EU and PRIME-ROSE, would enhance collaboration, streamline regulatory pathways, and promote consistent standards.

Next Steps: Future EU funding should be allocated to establish large-scale, pan-European clinical trials that specifically focus on advanced cancer therapies and can be accessed in multiple EU countries, thereby improving equity in access to innovative treatments.

Support decentralized clinical trials to enhance accessibility

Rationale: Many patients face logistical barriers to participation in trials, often due to distance from major research centers.

Recommendation: The EU should promote decentralized trials, which minimize travel requirements by leveraging telemedicine, local healthcare providers, and mobile health technologies.

Next Steps: EU funding should focus on building digital infrastructure and cross-border frameworks for decentralized clinical trials, including regulatory guidelines to facilitate patient access across regions.

Strengthen Quality Assurance and standardisation in genomic testing

Rationale: Standardizing CGP across laboratories is essential for consistent, reliable results, yet currently varies in quality and methods.

Recommendation: A centralized EU quality control framework should be developed, incorporating periodic proficiency testing, shared data repositories, and standardized protocols for CGP. This would ensure a unified approach to genomic testing across member states.

Next Steps: EU resources should support the creation of a centralized quality assurance body for genomic testing, which could offer training, certification, and tools for member states to achieve and maintain high standards in genomic testing.

Align reimbursement rates with real-world costs of comprehensive genomic testing

Rationale: Current reimbursement rates often fail to cover the full costs of NGS, limiting financial sustainability for healthcare providers.

Recommendation: The EU should advocate for reimbursement rates that reflect the actual costs of NGS methodologies. This includes expanding coverage to CGP, WES/WGS and RNA-based testing essential for detecting complex biomarkers in various cancer types.

Next Steps: Establish a standardized microcosting approach across member states, allowing for more accurate cost assessments and guiding policy decisions based on reliable financial data.

Develop advanced AI-based DSTs for clinical decision-Making:

Rationale: The complexity of NGS data requires sophisticated tools to support treatment recommendations, streamline interpretation, and reduce manual searches. WP10 (Oncology decision support tools) has been working on mapping current DST use and availability and has developed an EU-oncDST concept as described in D10.1.¹⁷

Recommendation: The EU should invest in developing AI-powered DSTs that can integrate genomic data with real-time clinical trial availability, patient history, and treatment guidelines, aiding healthcare professionals in making standardized and informed decisions.

Next Steps: Funded projects could focus on the development and testing of these tools, with particular attention to usability across different healthcare settings. EU-backed DST initiatives could also address data privacy and interoperability concerns to enable seamless integration into clinical workflows.

¹⁷ CAN.HEAL D10.1 EU-oncDST at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497907>

Promote ongoing training and multidisciplinary collaboration in precision oncology:

Rationale: Rapid advancements in genomics require healthcare providers to continuously update their knowledge and develop expertise in interpreting extensive genomic testing results. WP13 (Training and Education) has developed basic e-learning on oncogenomics and advanced courses for health professionals.

Recommendation: Implement continuous education programs across the EU to train oncologists, pathologists, and lab technicians, fostering a multidisciplinary approach to precision oncology.

Next Steps: EU funding should support educational and collaborative initiatives, including workshops, certifications, and digital platforms, that connect healthcare professionals and promote knowledge sharing in genomics and personalised medicine.

Integrate comprehensive genomic testing earlier in the patient care pathway:

Rationale: Earlier CGP/WES/WGS integration can provide patients with access to genome-directed therapies sooner in their treatment journey, potentially improving outcomes and reducing the need for last-resort therapies.

Recommendation: The EU should encourage CGP testing earlier in the disease course for patients with advanced cancer, supported by initiatives like "window-of-opportunity" trials that enable patients to explore innovative treatments.

Next Steps: Allocate funding to pilot programs that explore the benefits and feasibility of early CGP/WES/WGS integration, with a focus on assessing clinical and cost-effectiveness.

Engage industrial partners to co-fund evidence generation and implementation projects for genomic testing methodologies, creating a collaborative pathway for sustainable reimbursement decisions:

Rationale: Genomic testing methodologies, including broad genomic testing, liquid biopsy testing, and other advanced diagnostics, require robust evidence to support their integration and reimbursement in healthcare systems. A multistakeholder approach involving biotechnology and pharmaceutical companies can accelerate evidence generation and facilitate implementation. Industrial partners bring valuable resources, insights, and a strategic interest in supporting the adoption of these technologies.

Recommendation: Establish public-private partnerships in which biotechnology, pharmaceutical companies, and other industry stakeholders co-fund implementation projects and real-world evidence generation for diverse genomic testing methodologies. This

multistakeholder funding model would support the structured data collection needed to drive informed reimbursement decisions and equitable clinical adoption.

Next Steps: The EU should develop frameworks to engage industrial partners in funding real-world studies and longitudinal data collection on the clinical and economic impact of genomic testing methodologies. By incentivizing and structuring industry involvement, these partnerships can provide a sustainable approach to bridging the evidence gap, benefiting patients and healthcare systems alike, while helping overcome the evidence-funding paradox for reimbursement.

Integrate translational research components in EU-funded implementation projects

Rationale: Emerging technologies in precision oncology, such as multi-omics approaches, organoid-based drug screening, and liquid biopsy testing, require robust validation and real-world applicability assessments to facilitate their integration into clinical care. Translational research is essential for developing these technologies and ensuring their clinical utility.

Recommendation: EU-funded implementation projects (eg. JA PCM) in precision oncology should include translational WPs focused on developing and validating experimental technologies. In cases of budget constraints, at least biobanking efforts should be considered an integral component to collect and preserve high-quality, patient-derived samples. This approach ensures that valuable data and samples are available for future validation studies, potentially funded by other sources, and supports continued innovation in precision oncology.

Next Steps: EU funding should prioritize projects that, at a minimum, incorporate biobanking as a core element, enabling the collection of essential resources for future technology validation. This strategy leverages current projects for long-term research impact, helping to advance precision oncology across Europe through sustainable data and sample repositories.

8. Conclusion

The BALLETT study highlights the feasibility of implementing a standardized nationwide CGP approach and nMTB framework. However, challenges remain in drug and clinical trial access, quality assurance, physician training, and decision-making support. Addressing these barriers is essential to fully realize the potential of precision oncology in Europe.

By integrating these insights and adopting the recommended strategies, the CAN.HEAL project can drive progress towards equitable and efficient precision medicine across the EU. This will ensure that all cancer patients benefit from the advances in genomics and personalised treatment, regardless of their location.

The developed recommendations underscore the need for EU support in establishing a sustainable, equitable, and effective precision oncology infrastructure across Europe, focusing on next steps that require dedicated funding and policy coordination. The Joint Action Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM) will be one of the next steps towards this infrastructure.

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ANNEX 1

Study Cost Calculation of Performing NGS in Belgian NGS Laboratories

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June 2023

Introduction

Since July 1, 2019, Belgium has implemented the NGS convention for (hemato-)oncology, which established a fee of approximately 350 euros, which has since been indexed to approximately 360 euros. This rate applies to DNA NGS and was initially calculated for small DNA gene panels, primarily testing hot spot regions. However, the initial DNA hot spot panels are no longer sufficient, and an expansion of the ComPerMed indications, including many tumor suppressor genes that require sequencing of entire exons, now demands a larger DNA panel, higher sequencing costs, and more complex data analysis. For RNA NGS, there is no reimbursement, except for lung cancer and thyroid cancer, but only if the DNA NGS does not show a "driver mutation." The current RNA NGS reimbursement amount is approximately 560 euros. Serial, non-simultaneous execution of DNA and RNA NGS can lead to delays in starting therapy. Driven by clinician demand, several NGS laboratories therefore choose to perform simultaneous DNA and RNA analysis using NGS or perform RNA NGS to detect both expressed mutations and fusions.

Microsatellite instability (MSI) is an important tumor-agnostic predictive marker for response to immunotherapy (www.compermed.be).

For comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP; a very large panel that also allows MSI and tumor mutational burden (TMB) determination), Belgium, unlike many European countries, does not provide additional reimbursement.

The goal of this study is to map the actual costs of performing an NGS test in Belgian NGS laboratories to determine whether the current RIZIV reimbursement rate is cost-covering.

Methodology

The initiative for this study comes from the BALLETT NGS laboratory consortium following discussions in the NGS convention steering committee and in the CDX committee. The study period lasted only a few weeks. Six of the eight institutes with NGS laboratories involved in the BALLETT study were able to gather the necessary data and perform the calculations: AZ Delta Roeselare, AZ St-Jan Brugge, Jessa Hospital Hasselt, UZ Antwerp, UZ Brussels,

and UZ Leuven. This study aims to provide a benchmark across various academic and non-academic NGS laboratories of different sizes and with sequencers of varying capacities. Before calculating the costs, consensus was reached among the participating laboratories on the expenses to be included and several other variables. A standardized Excel template was used for this purpose and can be shared upon request.

The cost calculation was performed for both NGS panels in hemato-oncology and oncology, as well as for DNA panels and DNA+RNA panels and CGP. The panels studied vary in size (gene count range: 35 – 523, hot spot or whole exon coverage) and allow for MSI determination or not. CGP panels also allow for TMB determination.

Results and Interpretation

The results are summarized and visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Total costs for the analysis of a sample using various NGS panels (dots); only DNA (left); DNA+RNA (middle); CGP (right). Blue dots: Panels that also allow for MSI analysis. The dashed line represents the DNA NGS RIZIV reimbursement rate of **€360**.

For the DNA panels (dot plot left), the total costs range between €544.63 and €1,005.17 per test. With a reimbursement rate of €360 per test, all laboratories incur a significant loss, ranging from €184.63 to €645.17 per test. The costs for DNA panels that also allow MSI determination fall within this same range (blue dots).

For the DNA+RNA panels (dot plot middle), the overall costs are higher, as expected, ranging from €680.10 to €2,049.23.

Two laboratories also calculated the costs for their CGP panel (dot plot 'CGP'), resulting in nearly the same costs of €1,831.90 and €1,886.72, respectively.

Given the higher costs for DNA+RNA panels and CGP, and considering the same reimbursement rate of €360 (except in two indications if DNA NGS is negative), the loss per test is generally higher for these panels compared to DNA panels.

Conclusion

The standardized cost calculation of NGS tests performed by six Belgian NGS laboratories demonstrates that the current NGS reimbursement rate does not cover the costs for any of the currently used DNA or RNA panels in any laboratory. Furthermore, it results in a significant financial loss for all laboratories/hospitals.